

YOUTH ARE THE MAIN FOCUS OF NEW UZBEKISTAN

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Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada yangi O‘zbekistonda yoshlarga berilayotgan keng imkoniyatlar va ularning huquqlarini himoya qilishning xalqaro mexanizmlari tahlil qilinadi. Yoshlar huquqlarini himoya qilish shartlari va O‘zbekiston kelajagi tushuntiriladi.*

Kalit so‘zlar: *Yoshlar strategiyasi, BMT Bosh Assambleyasining Nyu-Yorkdagi sessiyasi, BMT Bosh Assambleyasining 72-sessiyasi, Inson huquqlari umumjahon deklaratsiyasining 75 yilligi, Yoshlar masalalari bo‘yicha agentlik.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье анализируются широкие возможности, предоставляемые молодежи в новом Узбекистане, и международные механизмы защиты ее прав. Будут разъяснены условия защиты прав молодежи и будущее Узбекистана.*

Ключевые слова: *Молодежная стратегия, Генеральная Ассамблея ООН в Нью-Йорке, 72-я сессия Генеральной Ассамблеи ООН, 75-я годовщина Всеобщей декларации прав человека, Агентство по делам молодежи*

Abstract. *This article analyzes the wide opportunities given to young people in the new Uzbekistan and the international mechanisms for protecting their rights. The conditions for the protection of the rights of young people and the future of Uzbekistan will be explained.*

Keywords: *the Youth Strategy, the UN General Assembly in New York, the 72nd session of the UN General Assembly, The 75th anniversary of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, the Youth Affairs Agency.*

The future of any country is formed by young people between 18 and 30 years old. Creativity, activity, social responsibility and professional training of young people are crucial for the stable functioning of any democratic society.

Today, there are 1.2 billion young people between the ages of 15 and 24 in the world, which is 16% of the world’s population. By 2030, the target date for achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the 2030 Agenda, the youth population is expected to increase by 7 percent to nearly 1.3 billion.

As young people increasingly demand fair, equal and progressive opportunities and solutions in their societies, the need to address the multifaceted challenges facing young people (such as education, health, employment and gender equality) stronger than ever.

Youth can play an important role in development and must be given the knowledge and opportunities they need to realize their potential. In particular, young people should have the necessary knowledge and skills to contribute to the economy; and they must enter the labor market.

For the first time in the history of the UN, a systematic strategy - “Yoshlarni jamiyat hayotiga jalb etish orqali demokratiyani mustahkamlash” - the Youth Strategy until 2030 was adopted. Uzbekistan is one of the ten countries in the world where this strategy is being implemented rapidly. that the Youth Parliament and the UN Youth Advisory Council were established in a short period of time in UN Uzbekistan; welcomed the adoption of many strategies, programs and financial instruments to ensure meaningful inclusion and empowerment of youth.

Realizing this fact, Uzbekistan spends more money on their intellectual, physical, spiritual and moral development.

At the 78th session of the UN General Assembly in New York, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, took the initiative to create a Working Group at the UN on supporting the development of youth in Central Asia. This initiative once again demonstrates the high level of interest in ensuring and implementing youth rights in the Central Asian region. In Central Asia, where nearly half of the population is young people, it is considered that issues related to the development of the new generation and the realization of their potential are of particular importance.

In addition, at the 72nd session of the UN General Assembly, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan put forward the initiative to develop an international legal document - the UN International Convention on the Rights of Youth. At the 75th session of the UN General Assembly, the head of our state called on the world community to support Uzbekistan's initiative to adopt the UN Convention on Youth Rights.

This initiative is of great importance in solving youth problems and eliminating inconsistencies in international documents related to the field. This initiative is increasingly supported by the international community. The “Do‘stlar” group on youth rights was established, whose main task is to support initiatives in the field of youth policy and to encourage efforts to develop an international legal document on youth rights.

An important place in the development of the youth rights protection system is occupied by the tools and standards adopted by intergovernmental conferences in regions such as Africa, Asia, the Pacific region, Europe, and Latin America. Most of these documents and standards were adopted within the framework of the UN. The number of international documents on the protection of youth rights in the last 30 years exceeded 10.

The first unique international legal document of historical importance, which includes basic human rights, is the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, which will be widely celebrated in 2023 for its 75th anniversary.

The anniversary of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights coincides with the 30th anniversary of the World Conference on Human Rights in 1993, which laid the foundation for the establishment of the Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights. These are two important steps on the way to further respect for human dignity.

On the eve of celebrating the 75th anniversary of the most important and necessary document for humanity, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan **“Inson huquqlari umumjahon deklaratsiyasi qabul qilinganligining 75 yilligini keng nishonlash to‘g‘risida”** was adopted. The decree envisages various programs and activities aimed at strengthening human rights and raising awareness of basic and universal human rights enshrined in international human rights documents.

The 75th anniversary of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and the 30th anniversary of the World Conference on Human Rights, the adoption of the Vienna Declaration and Program of Action is a moment to reaffirm and strengthen the commitment to the realization of youth rights.

In commemorating the 75th anniversary of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and recognizing that young people face particular challenges in realizing their rights and are often at the forefront of human rights cases, the UN High Commissioner for Human Rights Department of Human Rights established a Youth Consultative Group to develop, implement, monitor and implement the Human Rights 75 initiative. Within the framework of this initiative, youth

representatives, as well as organizations and institutions working on youth and youth issues, will have the opportunity to express their views on the present and future of human rights. will be used in the development of the “Inson huquqlari 75” Youth Declaration, which will be presented at the upcoming high-level event.

The young generation has always been the center of attention of the state, because the activity and mobility of this social group is a source for more consistent development of the country. Uzbekistan is a country where more than half of the population is young people under 30 years old. As of January 1, 2022, the population under the age of 30 is 19.6 million people, which is 55.6% of the total permanent population. That is why the priority of modern Uzbekistan is to ensure that the voice of young people is taken into account more in the process of making decisions at various levels.

In the new version of the Constitution, protection of the rights of states to education, health care, housing, employment, work and recreation, provision of personal, political, economic, social, cultural, environmental rights and its active participation in the life of society and the state The new norms defining promotion obligations are a clear evidence of the special attention paid to young people. As for the conditions for active participation in the life of society and the state, the state's obligation is to create a foundation for the development of young people in all aspects - intellectually, creatively, physically and morally.

Today, a number of large-scale measures are being implemented to ensure the protection of guarantees for the realization of rights and legitimate interests within the framework of the state policy regarding youth. The basis of the state policy regarding youth is the Law “Yoshlarga oid davlat siyosati to‘g‘risida”, which defines the basis of comprehensive support for young people. In particular, youth development is based on key elements of education, creative and intellectual development, employment and support for youth-led innovation. It is worth highlighting the work being done to strengthen a healthy lifestyle and educate young people in the spirit of patriotism. These components are an integral part of the contribution of all social institutions involved in working with youth in one way or another to youth development.

Institutional support for youth is provided by the Youth Affairs Agency, and in the neighborhoods, the position of youth leaders has been introduced since 2022, and they are showing their activity in the neighborhoods. Every young person is trained by the agency to get information about the support provided by this organization, as well as to register and get a preferential loan, to open their own business, to improve their skills, to get legal or psychological advice. A platform has been developed where it is possible to submit an application. 650 billion soums were allocated to support more than 700,000 boys and girls through the “Yoshlar daftarchasi”.

The development of mechanisms for deepening youth policy, such as the “O‘zbekiston yoshlari – 2025” concept, unified criteria for evaluating the effectiveness of work with youth, and the national youth policy evaluation index, continues.

In this regard, the active position of young people in this process is an equally important factor in the implementation of planned strategies. It is necessary to increase legal literacy, protect rights and interests based on the law, understand the life principles of the world community, and actively fight against local and international problems. These are tasks that young people should be passionate about and inspired to do in order to deliver high-quality results and make the world a better place.

For the first time, at the initiative of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev the World Conference on Youth Rights was held on August 12-13, 2020, which was proposed by Mirziyoyev at the 46th session of the UN Human Rights Council. As a result of the forum, the declaration “Yoshlar-2020: global birdamlik, barqaror rivojlanish va inson huquqlari” was adopted in Samarkand. This document emphasizes the importance of youth playing an important role in ensuring peace and security, sustainable development, and human rights, as well as the importance of active, meaningful and inclusive participation of youth in decision-making.

In order to strengthen cooperation in the field of youth policy, on September 15, 2023, the leaders of the Central Asian countries signed the “Yoshlarga oid siyosatning umumiy yo‘nalishlari to‘g‘risidagi kelishuvni” aimed at creating conditions for the wider involvement of young people in the social, cultural, political, social and economic life of the Central Asian countries.

Within this initiative, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev to unite the efforts of the states to develop the knowledge and skills of young people, to prepare them as mature qualified personnel and to establish a center for expanding the opportunities of Central Asian youth and realizing their potential, as well as in the field of combating the radicalization of young people. proposed to take measures to protect the young generation from the influence of extremist ideas by adopting a regional comprehensive program on cooperation.

As part of the implementation of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “Inson huquqlari umumjahon deklaratsiyasi qabul qilinganining 75 yilligini keng nishonlash to‘g‘risida”, the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan has organized “Yoshlar huquqlari: imkoniyatlar va himoya qilish mexanizmlari” dedicated to the 75th anniversary of the adoption of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights put forward the initiative to hold an international forum on “mechanisms”.

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